

Supporting Information

Joyce B. Matsoso; Email: matsosoj@vscht.cz

Zdeněk Sofer; Email: soferz@vscht.cz

Enhancing nitrogen reduction reaction through formation of 2D/2D hybrid heterostructures of MoS₂@rGO

Joyce B. Matsoso^{1, 2*}, Nikolas Antonatos^{1, 3}, Lukáš Dekanovský¹, Roussin Lontio Fomekong^{1†}, Joshua Elliot⁴,
Diego Gianolio⁴, Vlastimil Mazánek¹, Catherine Journet², Zdeněk Sofer^{1*}

¹ Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology in Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

² Laboratoire des Multimateriaux et Interfaces, UMR CNRS 5615, Univ-Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, F-69622 Villeurbanne Cedex-France

³ Department of Semiconductor Materials Engineering, Faculty of Fundamental Problems of Technology, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Wybrzeże Wyspiańskiego 27, 50-370 Wrocław, Poland

⁴ Diamond Light Source, Diamond House, Harwell Science and Innovation Park, Didcot, Oxfordshire OX11 0DE, United Kingdom

Experimental:

Figure S1: Synthesis procedure for anchoring MoS₂ nanosheets on rGO nanosheets.

Figure S2: Representation of the H-type electrolytic cell.

Results:

Figure S3: (a) SEM, (b-c, e) low magnification TEM and HRTEM micrographs of the pristine MoS₂ samples, as well as (d) SEM EDX mapping profiles.

Figure S4: AFM images and height profiles for the (a) and (b) MoS₂@rGO hybrid, as well as (c) pristine MoS₂ samples.

Figure S5: Adsorption isotherms of pristine MoS₂ and the MoS₂@rGO hybrid samples.

Figure S6: FT-IR spectra of pristine MoS_2 and the $\text{MoS}_2@\text{rGO}$ hybrid samples.

Figure S7: (a) XPS survey spectra of MoS₂ (*green*) and MoS₂@rGO (*red*), as well as fitted (b) Mo 3d + S 2s, (c) S 2p, and (d) O 1s spectra for MoS₂ nanostructures.

Figure S8: (a) NRR performance of MoS₂ nanocatalysts (NH₃ yield rate and FE) versus cathodic potential, (b) Yield rate of hydrazine (N₂H₄) after NRR experiments catalyzed by MoS₂ and MoS₂@rGO nanocatalysts, (c) Polarization curves in N₂ and Ar, as well as (d) Chronoamperometric (*j-t*) curves at various potentials of MoS₂ nanocatalysts in N₂ saturated 0.1 M KOH electrolyte.

Figure S9: (a) Polarization curves, (b) Overpotentials and (c) Tafel plots, and (d) Nyquist plots of the electrocatalysts during HER activity in 1.0 M KOH.

Table S1: Textual properties of pristine MoS₂ and the MoS₂@rGO hybrid samples

Sample	BET surface area (m ² /g)	Monolayer Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore vol. (cm ³ /g)
MoS ₂	45.5	10.4	0.2936
MoS ₂ @rGO	56.1	12.9	0.2698
rGO	185.8	42.7	0.7747

Table S2: Raman parameters for the pristine MoS₂ and the MoS₂@rGO hybrid samples

Sample	Peak position (cm ⁻¹)				Defect density ratio (I _D /I _G)	Δ (A _{1g} -E _{2g})
	E _{2g}	A _{1g}	D-band	G-band		
MoS ₂	381.4	406.1	-	-	-	24.7
MoS ₂ @rGO	380.6	406.4	1345.8	1587.7	3.17	25.8

Table S3: Atomic compositions of the composite samples

Samples	Elements (at. %)				
	C 1s	N 1s	O 1s	Mo 3d	S 2p
MoS ₂	39.41	14.87	2.88	17.24	25.61
MoS ₂ @rGO	56.72	6.77	5.15	12.08	19.29

Table S4: EIS analysis of pristine MoS₂ and the MoS₂@rGO hybrid samples post HER experiments

Sample	R _s (Ω)	R _{ct1} (Ω)	R _{ct2} (Ω)
MoS ₂	9.94	560	-
MoS ₂ @rGO	16.9	74.3	30.4